

EMP-APAC

Evaluating Vietnam Power Sector: An Analysis Using OSeMOSYS (2025–2050)

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Executive Summary

This report evaluates Vietnam's national Power Development Plan VIII (PDP8), utilizing the Open-Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) to analyze potential development pathways for the nation's power sector through 2050. The main objective of this study is a comparative assessment of three scenarios designed to explore the trade-offs between policy pathways: Business-As-Usual (BAU) scenario, a market-driven Carbon Pricing (CAP) scenario, and a target-driven capacity under the national Power Development Plan 8 (PDP8). The CAP scenario presents the most economically efficient transition, achieving emissions reductions at the lowest overall system cost. In contrast, the PDP8 scenario achieves the fastest and most certain decarbonization, aligning most closely to reach national net-zero goals, but at the highest upfront investment cost. The core trade-off is between the economic efficiency of market mechanisms and the practical investment. Recommendations emphasize that a balanced approach combining strategic state direction with market signals will be necessary to secure an affordable, reliable, and sustainable energy future for Vietnam.

1. Introduction

Vietnam's economy is one of the most dynamic in the world, a developing, mixed socialist-oriented market economy that has experienced rapid and sustained growth (Vo, 2023). This highlights the critical urgency of expanding both generation capacity and the grid infrastructure required to deliver reliable power and sustain the nation's economic momentum. The challenge of meeting surging energy demand is compounded by Vietnam's firm commitment to sustainable development and climate action. The energy transition not only is merely a technical or economic necessity, but

also is a core national policy objective. At the 26th UN Climate Change Conference of the Parties (COP26), Vietnam made a landmark commitment to achieve net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050. This pledge, supported by interim targets in its Nationally Determined Contribution (NDC), has fundamentally reshaped the country's long-term energy strategy (World Bank, 2022).

The primary instrument for realizing this vision is the national Power Development Plan VIII (PDP8). This official government roadmap outlines a radical transformation of the power sector, mandating a phase-out of coal-fired power generation and a massive scale-up of renewable energy. This strategy aims to leverage Vietnam's natural resources, including some of the best solar and wind resources in Southeast Asia, with an estimated technical potential exceeding 1,000 GW (EOS Intelligence, 2025). Beyond its climate objectives, this transition is also viewed as a strategic imperative for enhancing national energy security by reducing the country's growing reliance on imported fossil fuels and the associated price volatility (OECD Economic Survey, 2025). PDP8, therefore, represents the government's definitive blueprint for navigating the dual imperatives of ensuring energy supply for economic growth while fulfilling its international climate commitments.

In this context, the aim of this research is to quantitatively evaluate the potential impacts of Vietnam's Power Development Plan VIII (PDP8) on the national energy system's evolution through 2050. The primary research question is: How will Vietnam's power sector evolve under different policy implementations? To support the main research question, two sub research questions are: How would introducing a carbon price alter the technology mix and system costs? What are the technology and energy mix if the official PDP8 is implemented as planned?

2. Methodology

This study applies the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) to perform scenario-based analysis utilizing a long-term energy system optimization model. OSeMOSYS is selected for its open-source nature, which promotes transparency and accessibility, and its proven capability in modeling long-run energy planning and capacity expansion decisions

Three scenarios were developed and analyzed:

1. Business-As-Usual (BAU Scenario): This scenario projects the power system's development based on the continuation of existing policies and historical trends, without implementing the new and specific targets.

2. Carbon Pricing Constrained (CAP Scenario): This scenario assesses the impact of a formal climate policy by introducing an escalating carbon price on fossil fuel emissions forcing the model to internalize the cost of carbon in its investment and dispatch decisions.

3. PDP8 Implemented (PDP8 Scenario): This scenario models the direct implementation of the official targets outlined in the revised PDP8, approved in April 2025.

Feature	BAU	CAP	PDP8
Core Logic	Historical trends continue	Market-based emissions reduction	Target-driven government plan
Emission Target	None	None	Annual limits: 199 MtCO ₂ (2030), 27 MtCO ₂ (2050)
Key Policy Input	Limited new technology penetration	Carbon price of \$5-15/ton from 2028	Fixed capacity targets for 2030 & 2050
Coal Policy	None	None	Mandated phase-out by 2050
Renewable Target	None	None	28% (2030), 74% (2050) (excl. hydro)

Figure 1: Scenario Key Input

3. Results

The model's projections for annual electricity generation and total installed capacity reveal three different transformations of the power system. Under the **BAU** scenario, the power sector's evolution remains heavily dependent on fossil fuels, particularly coal and natural gas, with only limited penetration of new technologies. Consequently, capacity expansion is the slowest among the three scenarios, and the share of renewable energy in the generation mix sees minimal growth. This pathway represents a continuation of the status quo, failing to address the strategic imperatives of decarbonization and energy security. The **CAP** scenario illustrates the power of market-based mechanisms to drive change. The introduction of a carbon price from 2028 makes carbon-intensive coal generation economically uncompetitive, triggering a significant shift towards lower-emission natural gas and a substantial build-out of renewable energy sources. The model indicates a particularly massive expansion of solar power capacity under this scenario. As a result, coal is effectively phased out of the generation mix by the 2040s, driven purely by economic incentives. Finally, the **PDP8** scenario depicts the most rapid and radical transformation. Driven by mandated

government targets, this pathway features the most aggressive expansion of total installed capacity. The system becomes overwhelmingly dominated by solar and wind power, especially after 2040, leading to the fastest transition to a renewables system. Similar to the CAP scenario, coal generation is phased out by the 2040s, but here the driver is direct policy mandate rather than price signals.

Figure 2: Electricity Annual Generation (PJ)

Across all three scenarios, hydropower generation remains a stable and significant contributor, with its capacity approaching its maximum technical potential by 2050 in the PDP8 scenario. Furthermore, both the CAP and PDP8 scenarios project the emergence of geothermal power as a contributor to the energy mix by 2050, indicating its potential role in a decarbonized system.

Figure 3: Total Installed Capacity (GW)

The environmental outcomes of the three scenarios are significantly different. The **BAU** scenario presents a deeply concerning environmental future. With no proactive policy to curb fossil fuel consumption, emissions are projected to grow uncontrollably, reaching nearly 600 million tons (Mton) of CO₂ by 2050. This trajectory is in direct and severe conflict with Vietnam's national and international climate commitments, including its Net-Zero 2050 goal. In the **CAP** scenario, the carbon price acts as an effective tool for decarbonization. By making emissions costly, it incentivizes a shift away from coal and towards cleaner alternatives. The model shows that this causes emissions to peak around the year 2030 and then enter a period of steady decline as renewables and natural gas displace coal. But until 2040, there is a gradual increase, suggesting that the carbon price should be more aggressive after the market becomes saturated. This demonstrates that a market-based instrument can successfully bend the emissions curve downwards. The **PDP8** scenario achieves the most significant and rapid emissions reduction. This outcome is a direct result of the plan's explicit and aggressive policy levers: a mandated phase-out of coal and legally binding targets for renewable energy deployment. The model confirms that strict adherence to the PDP8 roadmap would place Vietnam on a clear path towards its 2050 net-zero target, resulting in the fastest decarbonization of the three pathways.

Figure 4: Annual Technology Emission (MtCO₂)

The economic analysis reveals a fundamental trade-off between the cost of the energy transition and the speed of decarbonization. The analysis indicates that the **CAP** scenario results in the lowest total discounted system cost. This finding suggests that a market-based approach, which allows the model to select the most cost-effective abatement options at any given time, represents the most "economically efficient" pathway to decarbonization. It achieves significant emissions reductions at the lowest overall cost to the economy. In contrast, the **PDP8** scenario incurs the highest total discounted cost, primarily due to the massive upfront investment costs required for its aggressive and rapid build-out of renewable energy capacity. While it achieves the most ambitious climate goals, it does so at the greatest direct economic expense, reflecting the high capital intensity of a renewables-dominated system. The **BAU** scenario, while appearing to have lower initial investment costs, ultimately proves to be an economically unfavorable path. Its continued reliance on volatile and increasingly expensive imported fossil fuels leads to high long-term fuel and variable operating costs. This makes it an economically risky and unsustainable strategy over the long term, in addition to its severe environmental consequences.

Figure 5: Discounted Cost (Billion USD)

Table 2 provides a consolidated summary of the key performance indicators for each scenario at the end of the modeling period in 2050.

Metric (at 2050)	BAU	CAP	PDP8
Renewable Energy Share (%)	Minimal (19%)	High (91%)	Highest (93%)
CO ₂ Emissions Level (Mton)	595	177	27
Total Discounted Cost (Billion USD)	Highest (828.5)	Lowest (755.0)	828.3
Primary Investment Type	Fossil Fuels (Gas)	Solar Power	Solar & Wind

Figure 6: Key Performance Indicators by Scenario (2050)

4. Discussion

A deeper analysis of the model's results reveals a critical trade-off between theoretical efficiency and practical implementation. The model, which assumes perfect predictions, identifies the **CAP** scenario as the most economically efficient pathway. However, implementing a stable and effective carbon price presents immense practical hurdles within Vietnam's complex regulatory landscape. Conversely, the **PDP8**, though modeled as more expensive, aligns with Vietnam's history of strong industrial policy. Its clear, mandated targets may provide the certainty needed to attract the massive private and international investment required for the transition, highlighting a disconnect between the model's optimal path and the most achievable one.

Furthermore, the ambitious renewable energy expansion envisioned in both the CAP and PDP8 scenarios is fundamentally contingent on overcoming the national infrastructure in the electricity grid. The rapid, geographically concentrated build-out of solar and wind power has already outpaced grid upgrades, creating severe congestion and forcing the curtailment of clean energy. This geographic mismatch between abundant renewable resources in the South and Central regions and the primary demand centers in the North makes grid investment the actual limited rate for Vietnam's energy transition. Consequently, the model's cost projections for the PDP8 scenario are likely significant underestimates, as they do not fully account for the parallel investment required in new transmission lines, energy storage, and smart grid technologies.

Successfully navigating this transition requires a stable and bankable policy environment to mobilize the necessary capital. The Direct Power Purchase Agreement

(DPPA) framework is a pivotal mechanism designed to unlock private investment, but its effectiveness is currently hampered by a lack of clear operational rules and persistent grid access issues.

While this study focuses on the technical and economic aspects of decarbonization, a critical next step is to conduct a comprehensive assessment of the socio-economic co-benefits. Future research should focus on quantifying the socio-economic co-benefits of decarbonization. This would entail detailed modeling of the net employment effects within emerging renewable energy sectors and assessing the improvements in public health outcomes, including the consequent reductions in healthcare expenditures, resulting from diminished fossil fuel-related air pollution. On the technological front, research into hybrid energy systems that optimize the integration of renewable sources with nuclear baseload power and emerging storage solutions will be critical for addressing energy security concerns. Such research should evaluate the potential contribution of advanced nuclear power, including Small Modular Reactors (SMRs), for providing reliable, non-emitting baseload capacity, and analyze the optimal integration pathways for green hydrogen to decarbonize across sectors. This approach should be coupled with techno-economic analyses of green hydrogen production pathways and their applications across transportation, industrial, and heating sectors.

5. Conclusion

The key lesson is that policy is the primary driver of the energy transition's direction, speed, and cost. While the ambition of PDP8 is vital for meeting climate goals, its success depends on overcoming an immense financial barrier. Therefore, the primary recommendation is for Vietnam to consider a hybrid policy approach. This would involve using the ambitious targets of PDP8 as the guiding vision but implementing a carbon price as the primary tool to drive investment efficiently.

The modeling results present three clear paths. A continuation of the **Business-As-Usual (BAU)** trajectory is untenable, leading to a future of soaring emissions, high and volatile fuel costs, and a failure to meet national climate commitments. The analysis highlights a central strategic dilemma. The **Carbon Pricing (CAP)** scenario offers what is, in theory, the lowest-cost path to decarbonization. It leverages the efficiency of market forces to find the most cost-effective solutions.

However, its practical implementation faces significant political and administrative hurdles in the Vietnamese context. In contrast, the Power Development Plan 8 (PDP8) scenario, while obtaining higher upfront investment costs, provides a clear and state-directed roadmap. This target-driven approach offers greater investment certainty and aligns with Vietnam's established model of strategic industrial policy, potentially making it more effective at mobilizing capital despite its higher modeled cost.

The ultimate lesson is that Vietnam's energy future depends on decisive and effective policy implementation. The choice is not simply between competing technologies like solar, wind, and gas, but between competing policy paradigms: market-led economic efficiency versus state-led strategic direction. The most resilient and successful pathway will likely be a hybrid approach that combines the clarity of long-term government targets with the efficiency and innovation driven by market-based mechanisms.

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